

Kinetics and Mechanism of Acid Bromate Oxidation of Tartaric Acid[†]

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The bromate oxidation of dextro- and meso-tartaric acids has been carried out in aqueous acetic acid medium containing mercuric acetate and sulphuric or perchloric acid in the temperature range 30-60°. The reaction exhibits first order dependence each in [bromate] and [substrate], and shows no stable complex formation between the oxidant and the substrate. The reactions are acid catalysed and the absence of water molecule participation in the mechanism has been indicated and discussed by using Hammett's and Bunnett's criteria. The decrease in dielectric constant of the medium increases the rate. Specific salt effect has been observed. A probable mechanism has been suggested. Related thermodynamic parameters are calculated using E_a , the sign and magnitude of these parameters being also in accordance with the implications of the proposed mechanism.

LITERATURE survey reveals that the oxidation of tartaric acid by oxidants other than hexacyanoferrate(III)¹ and peroxydisulphate² with copper(II) catalyst, manganese(III)³, chromic acid^{4,5} and thallium(III) with manganese(II) catalyst⁶ has not received much attention. Hence, we thought to study the oxidation of dextro-, meso-tartaric acids and the related compounds, viz. malic acid and butane 1,2-, 1,3-, 1,4-, 2,3-diols with potassium bromate which is a powerful oxidising agent with a redox potential of 1.44 V in acid medium. In the present study of bromate oxidations, the product bromide ion formed in the reaction mixture reacts with bromate to generate molecular bromine, which on accumulation oxidises the substrate along with bromate. Hence to eliminate bromine oxidation, which is much faster than the bromate oxidation, the product bromide ion has been suitably complexed as soon as it is formed by using mercuric acetate. Mercuric acetate added is not involved in the kinetics.

Experimental

Conductivity water was used throughout the study. Meso-tartaric acid (K.L.), dextro-tartaric acid (B.D.H., A.R.), KBrO_3 (B.D.H., A.R.) and mercuric acetate (S.M.) were further purified by recrystallisation. H_2SO_4 (B.D.H., A.R.; sp. gr. 1.84), HClO_4 (B.D.H., A.R.; sp. gr. 1.74) and the other salts, like Na_2SO_4 , K_2SO_4 , NaHSO_4 , NaClO_4 were of AnalaR (B.D.H.) grade and were used as such. Acetic acid (B.D.H., A.R.) was purified by fractional distillation after refluxing with chromium trioxide and acetic anhydride.

The reaction was carried out under pseudo-first order conditions, i.e. the concentration of substrate

being 100 times greater than that of the oxidant and was followed by estimating the unreacted bromate at different time intervals by iodometric method. The kinetic study was carried out using sulphuric or perchloric acid. The pseudo-first order rate constants were obtained from the plot of $\log C_t$ (C_t = concentration of bromate at time 't') against time. The second order rate constants were obtained by dividing pseudo-first order rate constant with substrate concentration. The final product formic acid was identified by the characteristic spot tests⁷, and carbon dioxide and bromide ion by their usual tests.

Results and Discussion

Effect of varying [oxidant]: Kinetic runs have been carried out at different initial bromate concentration in the range 4.00 to 20.00×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} keeping the [substrate] constant. The rate of oxidation increases with increase in the concentration of bromate and $\log C_t$ vs time plots were linear upto three half-lives. The pseudo-first order rate constants were independent of initial bromate concentration as shown in Table 1, indicating the first order dependence on [oxidant].

Effect of [substrate]: Inspection of pseudo-first order rate constants shows that k' varies linearly with both [substrates] in the studied range (Table 1; 0.10 to 1.00 mol dm^{-3} for dextro-tartaric acid and 0.05 to 0.50 mol dm^{-3} for meso-tartaric acid) and $\log k'$ against $\log$ [substrate] was straight line with unit slope. When the reciprocal of the observed rate constants are plotted against reciprocal of the [substrate] good linear plot was obtained passing through origin, indicating no stable complex formation between the oxidant and the substrate or it follows second order kinetics.

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TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING CONCENTRATIONS ON RATE OF REACTION BROMATE-TARTARIC ACID SYSTEM

[H₂SO₄]=0.50 mol dm⁻³, [Hg(OAc)₂]=0.002 mol dm⁻³, HOAc-H₂O=30-70% (v/v), Temp.=40°

Effect of [Bromate] [Tartaric acid]=0.10 mol dm ⁻³		Effect of [(+)-Tartaric acid] [Bromate]=1.00 × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³			Effect of [meso-Tartaric acid] [Bromate]=1.00 × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³		
[BrO ₃ ⁻] × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	k' × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	[Substrate] mol dm ⁻³	k' × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	k _{II} × 10 ³ (=k'/[sub]) dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	[Substrate] mol dm ⁻³	k' × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	k _{II} × 10 ³ (=k'/[sub]) dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
4.00	1.53	0.100	1.53	1.53	0.050	0.80	1.60
8.00	1.49	0.200	3.51	1.59	0.100	1.53	1.53
10.00	1.53	0.400	5.75	1.43	0.200	3.12	1.56
12.00	1.53	0.600	9.21	1.53	0.300	4.77	1.59
16.00	1.50	1.000	15.21	1.52	0.500	8.02	1.60
20.00	1.52	—	—	—	—	—	—

Effect of varying [acid]: The rate measurements have been made in the range 0.25 to 2.00 mol dm⁻³ with both the acids, namely H₂SO₄ and HClO₄. The rate increases with increasing acid concentration as shown in Table 2. The plot of log k_{II} vs log[H⁺]

A slope of unity from Zucker-Hammett's plot indicates, most probably that water molecule is not participating in the rate determining step⁸. This is also confirmed by slope (w) values¹² obtained from the Bunnett's plot. Data in Table 2 indicate that the rates are faster in sulphuric acid than in perchloric acid. This might be due to the further dissociation of sulphuric acid to SO₄²⁻ and H⁺, where the acidity is greater than the perchloric acid at equal molar concentration.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING ACID CONCENTRATION IN BROMATE OXIDATION OF TARTARIC ACID

[Tartaric acid]=0.10 mol dm⁻³, [Bromate]=1.00 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Hg(OAc)₂]=2.00 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, HOAc-H₂O=30-70% (v/v), Temp.=40°

[H ₂ SO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	k _{II} × 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	[HClO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	k _{II} × 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
0.50	1.53	0.50	0.76
0.75	2.87	0.75	1.12
1.00	4.60	1.00	1.72
1.25	8.06	1.25	2.34
1.50	13.43	1.50	3.45
2.00	26.88	2.00	6.14
(n)*	1.05	(n)*	1.10
(w)**	-7.00	(w)**	0.00

* Slopes obtained from Zucker-Hammett's plot.
** Slopes of Bunnett's plot.

Effect of varying [salt]: The effect of added salts like Na₂SO₄, K₂SO₄, NaClO₄ and NaHSO₄ have been studied in the range 0.25 to 2.00 mol dm⁻³. From Table 3 it is observed that the rate constants were increased with increasing NaClO₄ and NaHSO₄ concentration and decreased with increasing Na₂SO₄ and K₂SO₄ concentration, indicating a specific anionic effect on the rate of reaction.

is not linear but the Zucker-Hammett's plot⁸, i.e. log k_{II} vs H₀ is linear. The values of H₀ at various acid concentrations are taken from Paul and Long⁹ assuming that the values do not change much upto 50% (v/v) acetic acid medium^{10,11}. Zucker-Hammett's plot indicates the equilibrium involving H⁺ as

Effect of varying solvent composition: The effect of dielectric constant of the media on the rate of reaction has been studied by varying the percentage of acetic acid in the range 20-60% (v/v). The dielectric constants of different acetic acid-water mixtures at 40° are obtained by an approximate validity method¹². The rate constants increase with increasing acid content of the medium. A plot of log k_{II} vs (D-1/2D+1) rather than vs 1/D, is linear which is in good agreement with the Laidler and Eyring's equation for a dipole-dipole reaction. This observation indicates that the reaction is between two dipoles.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING ADDED [SALT] ON RATE OF REACTION IN ACID BROMATE-TARTARIC ACID SYSTEM

[Substrate]=0.10 mol dm⁻³, [Oxidant]=0.001 mol dm⁻³, [Hg(OAc)₂]=0.002 mol dm⁻³, Temp.=40°
[H₂SO₄]=0.50 mol dm⁻³, HOAc-H₂O=30-70% (v/v)

[NaClO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	k _{II} × 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	[NaHSO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	k _{II} × 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	[Na ₂ SO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	k _{II} × 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	[K ₂ SO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	k _{II} × 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
0.25	1.53	0.25	1.57	0.25	1.29	0.25	1.31
0.50	1.72	0.50	1.77	0.50	1.19	0.50	1.13
0.75	1.85	0.75	2.00	0.75	1.00	1.00	0.95
1.00	2.05	1.00	2.39	1.00	0.94	—	—
1.50	2.10	1.50	3.05	—	—	—	—
2.00	2.19	2.00	3.87	—	—	—	—

TABLE 4—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS IN OXIDATION OF DEXTRO- AND MESO-TARTARIC ACIDS BY ACID BROMATE

[Substrate]=0.10 mol dm⁻³, [Bromate]=0.001 mol dm⁻³, [Hg(OAc)₂]=0.002 mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄]=0.50 mol dm⁻³, HOAc H₂O=30-70% (v/v), Temp.=40°

Tartaric acid	k _{II} × 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	Temp. coefficient	E _a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹	-ΔS [‡] J mol ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹	ΔG [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹	log PZ
meso-	1.53	2.34	71.75	69.15	78.33	93.68	8.72
dextro-	1.53 (0.76)	2.39 (2.58)	71.78 (80.98)	69.18 (78.38)	78.23 (54.61)	93.68 (95.36)	8.72 (9.98)*

* Parenthesis values are in perchloric acid medium.

The temperature effect has been studied in the range 30 to 60° in sulphuric acid and perchloric acid at 30-70% (v/v) acetic acid-water medium. The plot of log k_{II} vs 1/T is linear. Activation energy (E_a) was calculated from the Arrhenius plot and using this E_a related thermodynamic parameters, namely ΔH[‡], ΔS[‡], ΔG[‡] and PZ were evaluated and are recorded in Table 4.

An interesting conclusion regarding the mechanism can be derived by a study of energy of activation (E_a) and entropy (ΔS[‡]). Chatterji and Antony^{14,15} have found E_a to be between 11 (46.02) and 13 (54.39 kJ mol⁻¹) kcal mol⁻¹, when monohydric alcohols are oxidised to the corresponding aldehydes by chromic acid. On the other hand Criegee *et al.*^{16,17} and Price and Knell¹⁸ have observed E_a values to be 22.1 (92.47) and 22.4 (93.72 kJ mol⁻¹) kcal mol⁻¹ in glycol cleavage by chromic acid and by periodic acid, respectively.

Bakore *et al.* have observed in the oxidation of tartaric acid by chromic acid⁵ and of diols by potassium permanganate¹⁹, E_a=18.6 (77.82) and 21.0 (17.86 kJ mol⁻¹) kcal mol⁻¹, respectively. E_a value in the pinacol oxidation by chromic acid as observed by Chang and Westheimer²⁰ in 21.0 (87.86 kJ mol⁻¹) kcal mol⁻¹. In the oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols with acid bromate studied by Sundaram and Vijaya Laxmi²¹, and Subramanian and Natarajan²², respectively, the activation energy values are reported as 15.0 (62.76) and 16.0 (66.95 kJ mol⁻¹) kcal mol⁻¹.

In the malic acid oxidation by bromate, E_a is 16.01 kcal mol⁻¹ (66.99 kJ mol⁻¹), ΔS[‡]= -24.4 e.u. (-102.14 J deg⁻¹ mol⁻¹); and for butane-1,4; -1,3; -1,2- and -2,3-diols, E_a being 15.25 (63.80), 15.34 (64.20), 15.00 (62.76) and 13.54 (56.62 kJ mol⁻¹) kcal mol⁻¹, and ΔS[‡]= -21.06 (-88.13), -18.25 (-76.36), -22.34 (93.42) and -24.31 (101.83 J deg⁻¹ mol⁻¹) e.u., respectively.

In the present bromate oxidation of tartaric acid, E_a value is neither 11-13 (46-54.4) nor 22.1-22.4 (92.47-93.72 kJ mol⁻¹) kcal mol⁻¹ but it is in between (Table 4). This suggests that the oxidation to carbonyl compounds is taking place simultaneously both in the normal way and by cleavage as shown in Chart 1. This has been verified by studying the products of oxidation.

Chart 1

Hence, it can be concluded that when H of C-H bond is attacked the normal way of oxidation to carbonyl products takes place but when H of O-H is attacked then the rupture of C-C bond takes place with the formation of cleavage products. Thus, in the primary and secondary alcohols the seat of reaction is the rupture of C-H bond in the α -position and in hydroxy acids O-H is attacked as shown in Chart 1.

From Table 4, it is observed that the rate constants and E_a values are same for meso- and dextro-tartaric acids unlike in manganic oxidations⁹, where the meso-tartaric acid gets oxidised about twice as fast as dextro-tartaric acid. For the higher rate for meso-tartaric acid oxidation by manganic ion, Waters and Levesley⁸ assumed a cyclic complex, where two potential hydroxy groups are participating in the reaction. But with bromate oxidation there is no change in the rate constants and activation energies. This indicates that there is no cyclic complex formation between the acid bromate and the tartaric acid, and both OH groups are not oxidised simultaneously. The rate constant is approximately same as that for the malic acid oxidation ($4.78 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$) by the same oxidant.

The intermediate in Chart 1, HOOC-COCHOH-COOH upon oxidation by either way (i) or (ii) produces a species identified by spot test to be glyoxal which gets further oxidised to final products. At the end of the reaction, CHO-CHO, COOH-CHO and HCOOH were present in the reaction mixture, at low bromate concentration, but at high bromate concentration only formic acid was observed. The formation of formic acid as the end-product of this reaction would essentially involve a number of stable and unstable intermediates all of which are not easily identifiable. Test for decarboxylation with the reaction mixture used for kinetic runs was not possible because of a large dilution. But with large amounts of reactants CO_2 could be conveniently detected by passing the gas into a weighed bulb containing potassium hydroxide solution whose weight was found to increase after some time. No induced polymerisation has been observed with acrylonitrile and acrylamide, hence the intermediates undergo oxidation through a series of successive two-electron steps leading ultimately to formic acid and carbon dioxide.

The rate expression obtained from the mechanism is

$$k_{\text{obs}} = K_1 k_2 [\text{Tartaric acid}]_0$$

where, K_1 is the formation constant of HBrO_3 and obtained as 0.5 l mol^{-1} from our earlier study. Using this value, k_2 has been calculated as $1.17 \times 10^{-2} \text{ l}^2 \text{ mol}^{-2}$, which explains all the observed facts.

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